

**The Future of Information Services and Digital Libraries:
The Case of LibGen and SciHub**

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Abstract

The largest digital libraries currently in free public access (LibGen and SciHub) are run by entities few would have expected to play a role in the propagation of scientific knowledge: highly resilient and organised groups of *digital pirates*. This paper examines, from the marketing science point of view, the data procurement methods, the economic models and the defensive systems employed by these digital libraries, and makes conclusions about the factors that are allowing them to flourish. The principal factors are: (a) the fundamental contradiction inherent in digital rights management (DRM) systems – the content, however strongly protected, must eventually be exposed in its original form to be readable; (b) economic unfeasibility of enforcing copyright on the Internet – the recent failed attempts by Elsevier are examined in particular detail; (c) emergence of influential left-wing political schools of thought regarding the "right" to information, particularly the so-called "open access" movement; (d) availability of high-bandwidth Internet connections, and of significant technical expertise, in countries that are fundamentally unfriendly to the Western legal system, including the copyright law; (e) emergence of financial transaction mechanisms that are beyond the control of nation states. The presence of these factors resulted in the appearance of vast publicly accessible libraries of – technically – copyrighted information. SciHub alone contains over 62 million academic papers and is currently serving over 200,000 requests per day. LibGen hosts approximately 1.6 million scientific and technical books, and 2.7 million fiction books. Both are flourishing; neither is going away anytime soon.

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M31: Marketing And Advertising / Marketing

H44: Publicly Provided Goods / Mixed Markets

Z11: Economics of the Arts and Literature

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P31: Socialist Enterprises and Their Transitions

1. Introduction

Information institutions (digital libraries, academic publishers, databases, search engines) are increasingly vital for the functioning of human society (Borgman, 1999, Fox and Sornil, 2003). These organisations are embedded into virtually every decision making process and every education programme, particularly in sciences (Apedoe and Reeves, 2006, Spink and Cool, 1999). Information institutions have the usual free market motivations – growth, sustainability, good financial performance. They are, however, special in many aspects that are unique to information technology outfits, and the purpose of this paper is to highlight a number of vulnerabilities that information institutions in general, and digital libraries in particular, suffer from. These vulnerabilities may well prove fatal for most digital libraries in the very near future, and it is not clear how (or if at all) they should be protected.

Our starting point is to observe that the largest digital libraries currently in free public access (LibGen and SciHub) are run by rather unusual – in the offline world – entities: organised groups of digital pirates. These groups appear to possess spectacular technical competence and operational security skills: some of them have been evading law enforcement for decades (Franklin, 2017). Far from being marginalised outcasts, both LibGen and SciHub are *flourishing* – SciHub alone contains over 62 million academic papers and is currently serving over 200,000 requests per day, mostly from scientists and engineers in the developing world (Bohannon, 2016, McNutt, 2016). LibGen hosts approximately 1.6 million scientific and technical books, and 2.7 million fiction books and has a similar traffic (Cabanac, 2016). This paper examines, from the marketing science point of view, the data procurement methods, the economic models and the defensive systems employed by these digital libraries, and makes conclusions about the factors that are allowing them to flourish.

2. Digital libraries – a pirates' market?

In the emerging global digital library system, two very distinct versions of information services currently exist. On the political right (private, profit-making) we have commercial publishers, such as

Wiley, Elsevier and Plenum; on the political left (state-owned, non-profit) we have the standard public libraries, enthusiast-run repositories such as ArXIV, and the emerging plethora of university-based data repositories that were created in response to government regulations and pressure from left-wing social justice groups, such as the UK Research Excellence Framework requirements for “open access”. This section argues that the right-wing system is vulnerable because it relies on a technically impossible feat of controlling access to digital information perfectly.

Consider Elsevier's unenviable current predicament, shared in all general details by the other major commercial publishers (Wiley, Tylor & Francis, ACS, RSC, IOP, *etc.*):

1. The excellent work Elsevier has been doing in its publishing business (the typesetting in its scientific monographs is a work of art), its digital library (ScienceDirect is exemplary) and its database branch (before the disastrous interface re-design, Scopus was also very good) has meant that it has enjoyed 40% profit margins – excellent performance on par with Silicon Valley giants, but a dreadful misdeed in the eyes of overwhelmingly left-leaning academics, librarians and media pundits (Heyman et al., 2017). Cue the many and varied calls for boycott, accusations of mistreatment and resignations of editorial boards. Whole countries have joined the fray – at the time of writing, Elsevier is threatening to cut off ScienceDirect access to the Max Planck Society. Clearly, turning a profit from what is (incorrectly) perceived to be exploitation of academic writers is a deadly sin these days.
2. The access agreements that Elsevier strikes with universities across the world are based on IP address ranges – any computer from within the network of a particular university would automatically be granted access. This does, of course, include any computer behind a network address translation layer that would look to the university IT security team like just another TCP/IP connection. This disastrous vulnerability is being masterfully exploited by SciHub – the notorious pirate repository simply has proxies (presumably set up by volunteers or friendly hackers) into over 150 major universities. To make matters worse, SciHub keeps a copy of every paper that its users download and serves subsequent requests out of the resulting local cache (Bohannon, 2016, McNutt, 2016). This has likely led to the site having a local copy of anything even remotely interesting, even though its local collection is, of course, not perfectly complete. Elsevier charges \$30 per paper (or hundreds of thousands of dollars per year for large campus agreements). SciHub charges nothing and encourages donations in the form of Bitcoin transfers. At the time of writing, the balance in the Bitcoin account associated with SciHub is BTC 62.89 (approximately £180,000).

3. It has proven to be in practice impossible to prevent authors from posting PDF files of their published papers online through a variety of means – from personal web pages to online collectives, such as social networks. For most physical science papers published after 2000, it is easy to find a PDF file online with sufficient search engine ingenuity, or even to request it directly from the corresponding author, who would normally oblige. With citation statistics as the primary current metric of academic performance, it is in authors' direct interest to disseminate their work as widely as possible in a readily accessible form – a direct conflict of incentives that authors are overwhelmingly winning at the moment.
4. The court system has proved ineffectual. Elsevier had sued Alexandra Elbakyan (the operator of SciHub) in an American court and won the default judgement after the defendant failed to appear (Schiermeier, 2017). American extrajudicial assumptions are ridiculous on the best of days, but trying to silence a Russian pirate operating out of Kazakhstan by an appeal to an American court is comical. In much the same way as it happened with Pirate Bay (Danaher et al., 2017), the site will likely continue operating even if its founder is eventually apprehended and jailed.

All four factors essentially mean that, while the intellectual property technically exists, it is impossible in practice to enforce or protect. Even the moral side of the question is not in the publishers' favour – where composers and artists could reasonably argue that their works are being stolen, the authors of academic papers, even though they technically sign a copyright transfer form during the publication process, essentially regard the work to be their own, and do not normally object (or even are flattered) by its unauthorised distribution. That is to say, MP3 style defence ("copying is theft"), which has helped shut down Napster and Kazaa in the MP3 heyday (Danaher et al., 2017), does not work here.

Another major factor is mathematical. It revolves around the concept of digital rights management (DRM) systems (Subramanya and Yi, 2006). Various DRM systems generally rely on encryption: the content is delivered in an encrypted form (usually asymmetric encryption, such as AES), where content creators have the public key and the device (HDMI endpoints and similar devices) have a tightly protected (usually in hardware) private key. The process has failed time and again, first with DVDs (Schriefer, 2002), then with Blu-Ray (Griffith, 2007), then with all media encryption and protection standards. Even Apple no longer bothers protecting its media content and focuses instead on making it sufficiently easy and cheap to access for piracy not being worth people's time. Interestingly, for all the social justice arguments about piracy in information access, these is a regressive situation: the more intelligent and technically sophisticated individuals would overwhelmingly benefit from piracy, to the detriment of the poor who would have to pay. The reason is that all DRM schemes essentially

mount to "security through obscurity" – the content, however well protected, must be deprotected completely before being played (Litman, 2017). A sufficiently sophisticated pirate can extract the decryption key from a single compromised device, and that breaks the entire standard. Not session, not copy, not a particular work – that breaks the entire system, like it happened with Blu-Ray. There is just one key that decrypts all Blu-Ray disks in existence, and this key was leaked (Griffith, 2007).

Coming back to the example of the PDF file: the only package that does enforce PDF access controls is Adobe's own Acrobat. There are plenty of scripts on the Internet that would simply strip off any printing or editing restrictions. An academic paper or a book is thus extremely volatile – if it was readable once to a single person, it can be instantly distributed to everyone everywhere. The number of jurisdictions that are unfriendly to the Western legal system or unlikely to cooperate with a request from a western company is quite large: SciHub operated from Kazakhstan (Bohannon, 2016, McNutt, 2016, Schiermeier, 2017). It is therefore infeasible to enforce any information-related copyright. Even if the leaker of any original file can be identified by some kind of digital fingerprinting, going after them is also not in practice an option as it would precipitate a public relations disaster for companies that are already publicly disliked.

Information market is therefore wide open to piracy and there are hard mathematical reasons why that will always remain the case. Commercial publishers are vulnerable, and the author is of the view that they will eventually disappear. Not only are they in an unfavourable economic situation described above, they are also under an orchestrated attack from the social justice lobby who view open access as a good in itself (Beall, 2012). So powerful are the SJWs that open access regulations in the UK have effectively been written into law – the forthcoming Research Excellence Framework specifically requires all work that is submitted for evaluation to be in open access at an institutional or a subject repository. Commercial publishing industry will be destroyed in one or two decades. An appropriate quote here would be from Ayn Rand (Rand, 2005): *"They let us vote on it, too, and everybody – almost everybody – voted for it. We didn't know. We thought it was good. No, that's not true, either. We thought that we were supposed to think it was good."* The writing is on the wall.

3. Can digital libraries only be free?

Given the fairly certain fate of commercial information providers, we are left with two options: either the pirates take over, or the governments do – and the outcome is far from clear. To get an indication of which side is likely to prevail, consider the two leading exponents of the pirate market – LibGen (a pirate library of copyrighted books) and SciHub (a pirate library of academic papers and books). Both have a history approaching a decade and both operate from shady areas (Russia and Kazakhstan respectively). Both have databases that are estimated to be in the tens of terabytes and

bandwidth requirements if the order of a terabyte per day (Bohannon, 2016, Cabanac, 2016, McNutt, 2016).

The market price for a 20-terabyte disk array is about £2,000; a computer with sufficient processing power to handle SciHub's 200,000 queries per day costs about £1,000; a 1 TB-per-day hosting service is another £500 a year. It takes one person perhaps a month to write the code in Linux/PHP/MySQL, and then the system runs unattended for years. This is the nightmare scenario – more or less the totality of human scientific publication output can fit into some clever kid's bedroom and be run off his pocket money (Schiermeier, 2017). The amount of good will that such a server would generate in the academic communities of the countries and institutions too poor to strike a million-dollar site license deal with Elsevier would transform the pirate into a global hero – witness Elbakyan's appearance in Nature Top 10 most influential women in science (Himmelstein et al., 2017). Pirates also tend to run minimalistic common-sense operations: SciHub's web site front page resembles that of Google. The site is convenient and easy to use.

Consider now the approach taken by the UK Government: requiring every university in the country to maintain a publicly accessible repository of all submitted manuscripts in a searchable form. Firstly, the costs are multiplied by the number of the universities (hundreds). Each must employ a person – from the author's experience, the totality of work done by the various departmental secretaries and IT administrators adds to more than one FTE, but let us consider 1 FTE an optimistic estimate. So that's costs of the order of £50,000 per institution per year – nationally, around £10M a year. The total that RCUK expends annually in subsidising open access fees at major publishers is also of the same order of magnitude. Subject repositories have very bad search infrastructure – Google usually does a much better job of indexing a university repository than the repository itself. From just sheer IT disaster statistics, some of them will go down, some catastrophically. And that's just the UK. The amount of legislative and organisational effort is vast. Globally, the figure is likely in the billions of dollars.

On the other hand, the only thing the pirate kid needs to really always do, is automatic backup – Dropbox will charge him around £500 a year for a 20 TB bucket. Not spilling his Pepsi on the server is about as much risk assessment and policy documentation as he is going to need. That is to say, the things are stacked in pirate's favour in a spectacular way. Even the public sympathy is on his side – Elbakyan receives enough donations to keep the site going and herself maintained. Given the wave of popular support currently commanded by Sci-Hub, it is unlikely that any action against the female scientist would be politically feasible in the near future – she would quickly acquire the same status as the one currently enjoyed by Julian Assange.

And here we come to the final factor that makes the scales fly off the hinges in the general direction of the pirates: cryptocurrencies. Until about 2014, it was technically possible to deny a pirate web site all means of financial sustenance by choking off the money supply: witness the difficulty that WikiLeaks had when its various financial processing partners deserted it. That is no longer possible – Bitcoin is beyond state control and looks like it will always be (Plassaras, 2013). Checkmate.

4. Conclusions

The arguments presented above lead information services and digital libraries to a no-win scenario for any kind of for-profit operation: they would find themselves unpopular within the vociferous SJW dominated environment, they would be unable to secure their principal sources of income against piracy, and they would be unable to compete, in the tight regulatory environment for the Western world (for example, regarding minors' access to information) against the pirates who face no such constraints. The conclusion is that any digital library must either be a pirate outfit sustained by donations or a pork-barrel government programme with all the attendant inefficiencies.

The principal factors that lead to this gloomy conclusion are: (a) the fundamental mathematical contradiction inherent in digital rights management (DRM) systems – the content, however strongly protected, must eventually be exposed in its original form to be readable; (b) economic unfeasibility of enforcing copyright on the Internet – the recent failed attempts by Elsevier are particularly illustrative; (c) emergence of significant left-wing political schools of thought regarding the "right" to information, particularly the so-called "open access" movement; (d) availability of high-bandwidth Internet connection and significant technical expertise in countries that are fundamentally unfriendly to the Western legal system, including the copyright law; (e) emergence of financial transaction mechanisms that are beyond the control of nation states.

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